

Fashion Class Classification Through Computer Vision: A Case Study of Bangladesh

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Abstract: Because of its high level of unpredictability and subjectivity, fashion is a difficult topic for computer vision. Fashion has become an important aspect of a person's everyday existence in modern culture. Asia is one of the leading textile and clothing exporters, and online shopping has grown dramatically in recent decades. Unfortunately, due to poverty and corruption, many developing nations are far from experiencing this reality. To make this a reality, an organized system is required, and computer vision can assist in making this a reality. Furthermore, Consumers choose to purchase online for a variety of reasons, including time, affordability, convenience, and availability, making e-commerce a significant potential for local and international trade in Bangladesh. Issues such as Covid-19 and the supply-demand ratio, as well as user experience problems such as the absence of a sufficient sorting mechanism, have had an impact on the sector. This article aimed to implement an image classification model in small datasets to extract features from human-worn fashion images in respect to the marketplace of Bangladesh. Four approaches were used to improve the performance of the model: dropout regularity, data augmentation, and transfer learning. Dropout regularity prevented the model from overfitting on the benchmark fashion MNIST dataset, while data augmentation increased validation accuracy by 8% and the F1-score from 0.68 to 0.78. Transfer learning was used on the VGG16 and GoogLeNet, with pretrained weights loaded from ImageNet. The model predicted that hats, shoes, and trousers were the best and long-sleeved upper body clothes like coats and pullovers were the worst. The resulting model can be used for a wide range of e-commerce applications. One of them is to automatically add links to social media posts that lead to an online shop that directly displays all articles of the extracted apparel from the social media post.

Keywords: Bangladesh, Fashion Attire Transfer, Image Classification, dropout, data augmentation, transfer learning,

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Introduction

People have been engrossed in self-beautification since primaevial times hence much evidence of beads and jewelry can be found in various ancient cultures. Self-styling is in-deed a hard ordeal. Due to the high level of variability and subjectivity, fashion understanding remains a complicated problem for computer vision. Unlike traditional problems which have consistent and specific definitions, fashion does not depend greatly on individual taste but also has an important

temporal component: outfits and garments are constantly falling in and out of style [20]. In modern society, fashion has become a significant part of a human being's daily life. Asia (especially China, Bangladesh, India) is one of the largest exporters in the garments and apparels industry. Furthermore, Online Shopping has increased significantly over the past decades. The rapid proliferation of the Internet gave rise to the concept and practice of electronic commerce (e-commerce). Most developing countries are far from experiencing this reality due to many factors which act as obstacles for e-commerce to flourish in many parts of the world, such as poverty and corruption [2]. Due to the significance of fashion and increment in online shopping, an organized system has become a necessity. Computer vision can make this necessity a reality. Apparel Industry has been massive in Bangladesh since long ago. The rapid growth in Garments sector has been influencing the economy of the country for a while now. Much research was done in this sector proving the accelerating growths of this sector. In this literature review some of those will be highlighted along with the reason of choosing my research topic and its feasibility. The reasoning will also be backed up using some relevant works done by some other researchers. Even though there are various papers on Visual Identification and Classification, I have found fewer papers related to Computer vision and Fashion.

Related Works

Bangladesh's economy has been dominated by the apparel sector since the early 1990s. Garments are the country's largest export, accounting for roughly three-quarters of total exports, and the industry represents the country's dynamism in the global economy. In addition, the industry is the primary non-farm formal sector that employs the poor. Most of the workforce is made up of women who have less education and have moved from rural areas. Thus, the garment industry is seen as helping to alleviate poverty in Bangladesh by providing higher-wage employment opportunities for the poor who would otherwise be engaged in low-wage economic activities in rural areas. Because of massive growth in this industry the orders keep on piling up. And all the Warehouse are struggling to keep track of their stock items manually. As the world has been growing rapidly in the digital sectors Bangladesh also needs to step up their game [10]. Over the last decade, the world has been swimming in a technological ocean, which has created numerous opportunities as industrial boundaries continue to shift. New industries such as social networking, smart technology, mobility, and big data have emerged from "blue oceans." Looking ahead, new trends like the Internet of Things (IoT) and technological advancements toward 5G mobile technology has been paving the way for new markets and industries, as well as further advances in big data. A panel discussion of industry leaders and researchers addressed these issues as well as the emerging technologies that are changing the world [6]. The rapid spread of the Internet gave rise to the concept and practice of electronic commerce, which has since become a common phenomenon in the world. Internet-based economic structures and information networks are the new business reality, as organizations and individuals enjoy the ease of purchasing commodities and services from foreign shores. Most developing countries, however, are still far from experiencing this reality due to a variety of factors that act as impediments to the growth of e-commerce [2]. Fashion item detection can be an important first step of various e-commerce applications for the fashion industry. This method is based on a state-of-the-art object detection method pipeline. Since locations of fashion items are in strong correlation with the locations of body joint positions, it is necessary to incorporate contextual information from body poses. Even though the e-commerce industry has improved a lot in Bangladesh and the fabric industry has also engaged themselves in this mayhem [8]. As fashion is captured in images, the fashion sector provides the perfect foundation to be supported by an image-based service or application that is built on an image classification model [18]. Some researchers have described a system that uses Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) for image-to-image attire transfer using and image processing methods that can transfer the clothing from a person's image to another person's image [19]. Some research in Bangladesh implied the following: E-commerce is rapidly expanding as a powerful manifestation of globalization. The rapid growth of e-commerce presents a significant opportunity for local and international trade in Bangladesh [9]. In another work [21], Images and text are used for cross-modal e-commerce search. With the widespread adoption of smart phones and the internet by all segments of the Bangladeshi population, the volume of

trade conducted electronically has increased dramatically. Consumers prefer to shop online for a variety of reasons, including time savings, lower prices, convenience, a larger selection of options, and product and service availability. As a result, businesses must understand global consumer expectations, attitudes, and behavior. The B2C (Business to Consumer) model is the most common in e-commerce [21]. Even though the clothing sector has got some success in getting international orders, keeping record of their products is also giving them a lot of troubles. It is high time they switch to something digital. Thus, this idea of digital Image classification in fashion industry came into fruition.

Study Significance

The existing literature and system have focused on either image classification or image-to-image attire transfer. So far, little has been emphasized on a combined system regarding both. So far, the existing method has only been applied for fashion segmentation and image to image attire transfer. There has been little quantitative analysis of fashion recommendations based on seasons. Bangladesh is advancing rapidly in Online-shopping, especially in fashion segments, but currently no system can help the users and the retailers to segment their choices. This paper evaluates the application of image-to-image attire transfer of data science in a real use case scenario. It provides preliminary insights on computer vision's application in the fashion industry and contributes to the growing area of computer vision in image processing. It also provides an opportunity to advance the understanding of the fashion segmentation of Bangladesh and presents opportunities for further improvement of the system. An Automated system for product sorting would lead to greater help for all the fashion brand owners in Bangladesh and help the consumer in their online buying experience. The Fashion industry and online shopping are advancing at an exponential rate. Furthermore, this study aims to develop a design model that implements the concepts of computer vision to improve the processes of human fashion classification for Bangladeshi retailers and image-to-image attire transfer for consumers. It will investigate the current product sorting process of the Bangladeshi online retailers, identify the key pain points, and propose a new computer vision-based solution to tackle identified pain points. It will also test the application of a hybrid fashion class classification solution in the computer vision architecture.

Fig. 1: Retail E-Commerce Sales Worldwide

Research Objectives:

The main objective of the study is to develop a design model that implements the concepts of computer vision to improve the processes of human fashion classification for Bangladeshi retailers and image-to-image attire transfer for consumers. Specifically, this study aims at achieving the following: To investigate the current product sorting process of the Bangladeshi online retailers, to identify the key pain points as well as relevant computer vision features that can be implemented, to propose a new computer vision-based solution to tackle identified pain points. to test the application of a hybrid fashion class classification solution in the computer vision architecture.

Computer Vision:

According to IBM, Computer vision is a field of artificial intelligence that enables computers and systems to derive meaningful information from digital images, videos, and other visual inputs. If AI enables computers to think, computer vision enables them to see, observe and understand. Computer vision trains machines to perform these functions, but it must do it in much less time with cameras, data and algorithms [24].

Fig. 2: A rough timeline of some of the most active topics of research in computer vision. From 1970-2000 [14]

When computer vision first started in the early 1970s, it was viewed as the visual perception component of an ambitious agenda to mimic human intelligence and to endow robots with intelligent behavior [14]. If we look at modern-day implementation, we can say that computer vision has become an important part of the technological community. Fashion, mainly conveyed by computer vision, has become one of the world's largest industries [4].

Fig. 3: Relationship between images, geometry, and photometry, as well as a taxonomy of the topics covered in this book. Topics are roughly positioned along the left-right axis depending on whether they are more closely related to image-based or geometry-based [14]

Image Classification:

Fashion image retrieval (FIR) is a challenging task, which requires searching for exact items accurately from massive collections of fashion products. Despite recent advances, FIR still has limitations for application to real-world visual searches. Fashion images are vulnerable to shape deformations and suffer from inconsistency between the user's query images and refined product images [17]. A typical supervised machine learning function looks as simple as the following:

$$Y = f(x) \quad (1)$$

where Y is the predicted outcome, f is an unknown function and X represents the input data [23].

Facial Product reference: Facial geometry beautification mainly aims to enhance the attractiveness of facial shapes and components. This kind of technology is helpful for plastic surgery. Digital facial beautification makes it possible for a patient to view the outcome during an early stage of the operation before it takes place [12]. Currently, TAOBAO is using a feature that allows users to take photos and it will refer to the products which are related to their skin problems. One can also add their physical measurements to get the perfect sizes needed for the clothing that they need to buy.

Fig. 4: Product Trial Refence TAOBAO

Research Methodology

Algorithms

This system will be using a variety of neural networks. A neural network is a network or circuit of neurons, or in a modern sense, an artificial neural network, composed of artificial neurons or nodes [22]. Neural Networks use a basis function that follows the same form as Linear models for regression and classification [5].

$$y(x, w) = f\left(\sum_{j=1}^M w_j \varphi_j(x)\right) \quad (2)$$

where $f(\cdot)$ is a nonlinear activation function in the case of classification and is the identity in the case of regression. This model is extended by making the basic functions $\varphi_j(x)$ depend on parameters and then to allow these parameters to be adjusted, along with $\{w_j\}$, during training [3].

Artificial Neurons

An artificial neuron is the basic element of an artificial neural network (ANN) and performs the network's computational operations [28]. It receives two or more inputs from other neurons via weighted links and enters the weighted sum of these inputs into its activation function [29], adds the bias value, and generates a single output, which can be broadcasted as an input to many other neurons [27].

Fig. 5: An Artificial Neuron [27].

To calculate the weighted sum of the input components, the following formula is used:

$$Y_k = \varphi(Y_k) = \varphi(\sum_{i=1}^n w_{ik} x_i + b_k) \quad (3)$$

where Y_k denotes the weighted sum of the k th neuron's n input parameters, x_i and n , w_{ik} denotes the weight parameters received from the previous layer, and b_k denotes the bias value for the k th neuron. To obtain the neuron k 's output, the weighted sum Y_k is fed into an activation function [30]. The neuron will be trained to produce the desired output by adjusting the weights over several training cycles [27].

It is now strongly advised to use the rectified linear unit (ReLU) in more modern neural networks. The ReLU function computes the output using a ramp with

$$f(x) = \max(0, x) \quad (4)$$

The ReLU function returns x if x is positive and zero if x is negative [7], introducing nonlinearities to the decision function and network without affecting the receptive fields of convolution layers [31]. Other functions can also be used to increase nonlinearity, for example the saturating hyperbolic tangent,

$$f(x) = \tanh(x) \quad (5)$$

$$f(x) = |\tanh(x)| \quad (6)$$

these two equations represent the hyperbolic tangent function for ReLU in both normal and other results in absolute value. and the sigmoid function,

$$\sigma(x) = (1 + e^{-x})^{-1} \quad (7)$$

Here $\sigma(x)$ is the sigmoid function, and e^{-x} is the exponential function. ReLU is often preferred to other functions because it trains the neural network [1] faster without a significant penalty to generalization accuracy [32]. In multiclass classification problems, the softmax activation function is used to generate an output between 0 and 1 for each class. This output is interpreted as the class probability [3].

CNN Models

Convolutional neural networks are deep learning algorithms that extract information from input pictures by convolving them with filters or kernels [25]. After each action, the window moves, and feature maps learn the features [33]. CNN combines multiresolution decomposition and residual learning to learn to remove these artifacts while preserving image structure [15]. The size of the output matrix with no padding is shown, and the convolution process is shown in Equation. Padding is used to maintain the size of the supplied picture [34].

$$NXN * fXf = N - F + 1 \quad (8)$$

$$O = \sigma(b + \sum_{i=0}^2 \sum_{j=0}^2 w_{i,j} h_{a+i,b+j}) \quad (9)$$

$$NXN * f * f = (N + 2P - f)/(s + 1) \quad (10)$$

In this equation, O is the output, P is the padding, s is the stride, b is the bias, σ is the sigmoidal activation function, w is a 3x3 weight matrix of shared weights, and $h_{a+i,b+j}$ is the input activation at position x, y. CNN has applications in large-scale image identification[1], emotion detection through speech [36], facial expression recognition [35], biometric systems, genetics, and many other domains.

GAN

GANs are proposed to generate more realistic images by training a network to attend to parts of the image and generate images step by step [11]. The adversarial modeling framework is most straightforward when the models are both multilayer perceptron [7].

$$\min_G \max_D V(G, D) = E_{x \sim p_{data}} [\log D(x)] + E_{z \sim p_z(z)} [\log (1 - D(G(z)))] \quad (11)$$

Liquid Warping

Liquid Warping is a method that uses 2D key points to estimate human body structure [13]. This algorithm along with image segmentation will be used to model the virtual dressing room which is for the consumers.

Research Design and Data Acquisition

Research design involves an entire process mapping and modelling exercise to describe and analyze the current processes. Data collection is done in two separate areas: primary and secondary. Primary data is collected by extensive research of the subject matter and its corresponding applications. Secondary data is collected through survey, Interviews, article reading, and test running existing systems. Data accumulation is done through surveys to measure the necessity of the research.

Fig. 6: Online Shopping Status of Bangladesh

And when the question was asked about their reason for online shopping, they said its more convenient. The same question was asked to the business owners; they also confirmed their sales are better online than physical stores. So, as we can see more and more people are turning towards online platform. Next, the business owners were asked if they need any solution to sort their products and this was the result:

Fig. 7: Status of Online Solution necessity in Business owners.

From the chart it is clearly seen that more than 50% business owners want an online solution to sort their products. Around 23% people are interested in keeping their previous recording systema s well as they are willing to venture into the online system. Some are way too into the traditional system of Bangladesh. Which is to keep a thick ledger where they keep record of all the items in their stocks. These are mostly local shop owners with low educational background. The third and final research was done to ask the e-commerce buyers about the product trials. I asked them if they are always satisfied with their purchase and what if there was a better solution to try. Most of them agreed and here is result.

Fig. 8: Attire Transfer Necessity

50% users were very interested in the attire transfer system. But around 32% responders said they are concerned about their privacy and were unwilling to use a system where they will have to be on live camera. Some users preferred the current ongoing system where you will have to share your measurements with the buyer, and they will select the size for you. And some responders showed absolutely no interest in such methods. Several interviews were also conducted

to several garments’ owners and online apparel business owners. They all were asked if they feel the hassle and necessity of a better solution. Almost all of them answered the same way that a better solution is very much needed for Bangladesh.

System Design

The Following Diagram is for how the system works and a graphical representation of the system.

Fig. 9: System Design Business Owner Section

Fig. 10: System Design Consumer Section

Evaluation & Result

Several approaches were taken to train and test the model. For this system, tensorflow, keras have been used exclusively [16]. The following table shows the best-performing models trained on fashion MNIST to find the best model to work on fashion data [26]. The input shape of the images was 28 by 28 pixels and each max pooling layer cut the image in half, so a maximum of four convolutional layers could be used. All models were built with the following parameters:

Table 1: Testing Model Parameters

Parameters	Description
Loss	categorical_crossentropy
Optimizer	adam
Metrics	accuracy

Finally, the model was trained with following settings.

Table 2: Training Model Parameters

Parameters	Description
Train_generator	train_generator.flow_from_directory([path_to_directory]).
Steps_per_epoch	train_dataset_size/batch_size.
Epochs	50

Validation data	test_generator.flow_from_directory([path_to_parent_directory])
Validation steps	test_dataset_size/batch_size

The architecture column in the following table defines the layers that were used to construct the model. The model had three convolutional layers, the input layer containing 32 filters, the second 64, and the third 128, and two dense layers used to classify the data. The validation accuracy column displays the model's evaluated accuracy for training under the following conditions.

1. Without Dropout Layer
2. With Dropout Layer

Table 3: One-model approach evaluation

Number	Architecture	Validation Accuracy	
		(1)	(2)
1.1	2 Convolutional (32, 64) 2 Dense (64, 10)	92%	93.14%
1.2	2 Convolutional (32, 64) 3 Dense (128, 64, 10)	92.47%	92.61%
1.3	2 Convolutional (32, 64) 4 Dense (128, 64, 32, 10)	91.4%	92.86%
1.4	3 Convolutional (32, 64, 128) 2 Dense (128, 10)	91.67%	93.13%
1.5	4 Convolutional (32, 64, 128, 256) 2 Dense (128, 10)	90.04%	90.56%
1.6	3 Convolutional (32, 64, 128) 3 Dense (128, 64, 10)	92.02%	93.29%
1.7	4 Convolutional (32, 64, 128, 256) 3 Dense (128, 64, 10)	90.06%	91.21%
1.8	3 Convolutional (32, 64, 128) 4 Dense (256, 128, 64, 10)	92.09%	93.33%
1.9	4 Convolutional (32, 64, 128, 256) 4 Dense (256, 128, 64, 10)	90.6%	91.42%
1.10	4 Convolutional (32, 128, 256, 512) 4 Dense (256, 128, 64, 10)	90.23%	91.89%
1.11	3 Convolutional (64, 128, 256) 3 Dense (256, 128, 10)	92.25%	94.02%
1.12	2 Convolutional (64, 128) 2 Dense (128, 10)	92.15%	92.91%

The layers used to create the model were defined in the table's architecture column, which contained three convolutional layers: 32 filters, 64 filters, and 128 filters. To categorize the data, two dense layers were used: the first layer had 128

neurons and the last layer had 10 neurons, each representing one of the ten fashion categories. The validation accuracy of the various models did not differ much, with all models obtaining higher than 93% validation accuracy. The number of completely linked layers and units has no discernible influence on validation accuracy. When trained without dropout layers, Model 1.11, the model with the greatest validation accuracy, attained a training accuracy of 99.27% and correctly identified virtually every single training picture. However, when it had to process new, unknown data, the accuracy dropped by 7%, to a final validation accuracy of 92.02%. This can be explained by overfitting, as the network tended to capture and memorize image features rather than learning them.

Fig. 11: Training and validation accuracy of model 1.11 without dropout layers

The following figure shows the same model trained with dropout layers, and the difference is quite noticeable. When dropout was used, the gap between training and validation accuracy almost disappeared.

Fig. 12: Training and validation accuracy of model 1.11 with dropout layers

Dropout regularization can help prevent overfitting and improve the models' generalization abilities for new data. To illustrate this, models 1.4, 1.9, 1.10, and 1.12 were introduced and compared. Model 1.4 had one more convolutional and max pooling layer than model 1.9 and model 1.10 had 495,434 trainable parameters, while model 1.12 had over 1.6 million. This one extra convolutional significantly reduced the number of parameters fed into the fully connected layers, resulting in a lower number of parameters in the model.

Table 4: Model training performance.

Model	Total Parameters	Training Time
1.4	503,690	1 h and 3 min
1.9	495,434	1 h and 9 min
1.10	1,685,770	2 h and 26 min
1.12	2,435,210	1 h and 57 min

Finally, it is critical to determine the optimal number of convolutional layers for successfully extracting features while maintaining solid performance by reducing the model's total parameters. It is worth noting that using or not using dropout layers had no discernible effect on training time.

Table 5: Evaluation table for the second approach

Model	Data Augmentation	Drop-out	Training Time	Validation Accuracy	F1-Score

2.1	no	no	79 min	68.74%	0.63
2.2	no	yes	35 min	70.04%	0.66
2.3	yes	yes	42 min	78.16%	0.75

The two approaches to validation of a neural network yielded different results. Without dropout and data augmentation, the model achieved a validation accuracy of 68.74% and an F1-score of 0.63. With dropout, the neural network achieved 70.04%, and it took 35 min to train over 50 epochs. With data augmentation and training, the network achieved 78.16%, and training took 42 min. The model resulted in a final score of 0.75.

Table 6: Evaluation table for the third approach

Model	Training Time	Validation Accuracy	F1-Score
3.1	12 min	62.12%	0.38
3.2	20 min	65.55%	0.40

In the third Approach transfer learning conserved computational resources and could significantly reduce neural network training time. The training phase only took 12 minutes, which was 30 minutes less than models trained without transfer learning. The validation accuracy decreased by 16% to 62.12%. The fashion MNIST dataset was unsuitable for transfer learning due to its low F1-score of 0.38. The second test case resulted in a better accuracy than the first approach. But the accuracy is still very low.

Table 7: Transfer learning with the ImageNet dataset using VGG-16 and GoogLeNet. Number

Model	Transferred Model	Training Time	Validation Accuracy	F1-Score
4.1	VGG-16	1 h 47 min	83.96%	0.83
4.2	GoogLeNet/Inception	59 min	74.63%	0.71

The F1-score is a good metric for comparing different classification models and the transferred VGG-16 classifier outperformed GoogLeNet. Transfer learning was successful in this case study, as the transferred VGG-16 outperformed model 2.2 by improving the F1-score from 0.78 to 0.83, as well as the validation accuracy from 79% to 83%. However, the training time was reduced by 45 minutes, making it take 45 minutes longer to train.

Conclusion

This article aims to implement an image classification model in small datasets to extract features from human-worn fashion images in respect to the marketplace of Bangladesh. Convolutional neural networks are the undisputed standard for image classification tasks, and methods such as dropout regularity, data augmentation, and transfer learning should be used to avoid overfitting and improve model generalization. Four approaches were defined and implemented to see if and how the performance of a classification model trained on a small dataset could be improved. Dropout successfully prevented the model from overfitting on the benchmark fashion MNIST dataset, while data augmentation increased validation accuracy by 8% and the F1-score from 0.68 to 0.71. Transfer learning was used on the VGG16 and GoogLeNet datasets, with pretrained weights loaded from ImageNet.

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